

EVALUATION OF EQUIVALENT STIFFNESS MODELS FOR ESTIMATING MODAL VIBRATION CHARACTERISTICS OF COMPOSITE GRID STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY: Recent efforts to develop and evaluate equivalent stiffness models for estimation of modal frequencies of composite grid structures are summarized. The motivation for this work is that, instead of having to generate complicated 3-D finite element (FE) models of grid structures, a simple equivalent stiffness model (ESM), or finite element plate model having equivalent stiffnesses, can be developed for the prediction of the modal frequencies easily and economically. “Exact” finite element models of both orthogrid and isogrid structures have been developed to calculate the modal frequencies and corresponding mode shape for three different boundary conditions; free-free, cantilever and simply supported. Simple ESM finite element plate models of the same structures have also been developed for the same purpose. A closed form solution for laminated plates was also used to predict the frequencies for the simply supported case. Finally, the modal frequencies of small laboratory-sized composite grid structures fabricated by thermoplastic stamping were determined experimentally by using an impulse-frequency response method. Comparisons of the results show that the equivalent stiffness models can estimate the modal frequencies and mode shapes of the actual grid structures reasonably well. It takes a considerable amount of time to develop and run “exact” finite element models of grid structures having a large number of elements. However, the ESM is actually a simple plate model which converges very quickly, has considerably fewer number of elements and much faster analysis time than the “exact” finite element model.

KEYWORDS: composite grids, isogrids, orthogrids, modal frequencies, equivalent stiffness models

INTRODUCTION

Grid stiffened geodesic structural configurations date back to the 1920's [1] when they were first used in aircraft construction with a metal grid and fabric skin. The structures of these aircraft were known for their excellent tolerance to battle damage. The maturation of composite material technology permitted the creation of woven stiffening grids in the 1970's, and there has been slow but steady and continuous interest in composite grid structures for the last three decades. Composite grid structures are a promising concept for applications in plate or shell-like components of systems such as spacecraft, aircraft, automobile, containers, bridges, ships and propellers. These structures have several advantages over traditional construction methods that use panels, sandwich cores and/or expensive framework. As the ribs of the grids are made of unidirectional continuous fiber-reinforced composites, they are strong, tough, damage tolerant and do not delaminate. As grids are open structures, they are easy to inspect and repair. The potential also exists for completely automating the fabrication process that can reduce the processing cost. These uses and advantages demand the understanding of the behavior and characteristics of grid structures. One of the reasons that the application of these structures has been hampered is the absence of a clear understanding of their properties and behavior, particularly their dynamic behavior. The present study addresses the need for simple models to predict the dynamic behavior of these structures. Though

considerable work has been done to understand the static behavior of grid structures, the dynamic behavior of grids, without the skin or face has not received much attention. The present work deals with the estimation of the natural frequencies of orthogrids (Figure 1) and isogrids (Figure 2) in a very simple way to avoid complicated finite element models, and this will save time and money. Equivalent stiffness models (ESM) have been developed from the static analysis of Chen and Tsai [2] and applied to both closed form solutions for symmetric laminated composite plates [3] and simple 2-D finite element plate models in order to estimate the natural frequencies and mode shapes of grid structures. These results are then compared with results from “exact” 2-D finite element models and with experimental results to assess the accuracy of the estimations.

Fig. 1 Orthogrid

Fig. 2 Isogrid

OBJECTIVES

A systematic study was made to develop an equivalent stiffness model (ESM) to estimate modal parameters of composite orthogrid and isogrid structures under different boundary conditions (i.e., to assess the general applicability of the ESM in the prediction of modal behavior of grids). The overall objectives of the present study were:

1. Create “exact” 2-D finite element models of both orthogrid and isogrid composite structures for the prediction of the modal frequencies and mode shapes under different boundary conditions.
2. Develop equivalent stiffness models (ESM) to predict the stiffnesses of the same grid structures.
3. Create simple 2-D finite element plate models and closed form-laminated plate models having stiffnesses equivalent to those of the grid structures and use them to estimate the modal frequencies and mode shapes of the grid structures under different boundary conditions.
4. Fabricate specimens of orthogrid and isogrid structures and measure their modal frequencies for different boundary conditions.
5. Compare the ESM analytical results with “exact” finite element results and with experimental results.

ANALYTICAL METHODS

In the present work, several analytical models were used to predict the modal frequencies and mode shapes and to compare with each other. The “exact” 2-D finite element models of the grids were used to predict the “exact” frequencies and mode shapes. The natural frequencies and mode shapes of orthogrids and isogrids were calculated for free-free, cantilever and simply supported boundary conditions. The second type of model (ESM) was a simple finite element model of a rectangular plate having stiffnesses

equivalent to those of the grids. Frequencies and mode shapes of these models can be calculated for any boundary condition as with the previously described exact finite element models. The closed form frequency equation for a rectangular laminated plate [3] was considered as the third model, but the frequencies can be predicted only for the simply supported case for this model.

“Exact” Finite Element Models. The actual grid geometry was modeled using “exact” models, and these models calculated the modal frequencies and mode shapes of the grid structures with greatest accuracy. Models were prepared in the HYPERMESH pre-processor [4] and analyzed by using the ABAQUS solver [5]. The results were then displayed in the HYPERMESH post-processor. 2-D S4 shell elements were used. Though a 3-D finite element model would give the greatest accuracy as it takes into account the through-the-thickness deformations and stresses, it was felt that these deformations and stresses were not significant here because the grid thicknesses were much smaller than the in-plane dimensions. These are called general purpose shell elements [5] and they allow transverse shear deformation. They use thick shell theory as the shell thickness increases and become discrete Kirchhoff thin shell elements as the thickness decreases; the transverse shear deformation becomes very small as the shell thickness decreases. The *SHELL SECTION option in ABAQUS was used to define the section behavior. The geometric shape was the same as the grooves in the steel molds that were used to make the of orthogrid and isogrid specimens used in the experiments. The overall dimensions of the grid structure were 264 mm × 304 mm. The thickness of the ribs was taken as 6.3 mm and the rib width as 6.4 mm.

The input material properties for the Twintex® unidirectional E-glass/polypropylene composite of 0.45 fiber volume fraction were estimated by micromechanics. The material coordinate axis x was taken as parallel to the fiber direction, axis y as the transverse direction and axis z as perpendicular to the plane of the ribs (Fig. 3). In the finite element model, a global coordinate system (1, 2, 3) was chosen such that the coordinate axes were parallel and perpendicular to the zero degree ribs. Then the other ribs were oriented with respect to the zero degree ribs.

Fig. 3 Family of parallel ribs

Fig. 4. Equivalent stiffness model

Equivalent Stiffness Models (ESM). The second type of model (ESM model) is a rectangular plate model that has stiffness parameters which are equivalent to those of the actual grid structure (Fig. 4). Equivalent stiffness properties are used as input to either closed form solutions or finite element models to predict frequencies and mode shapes. As with the “exact” finite element models, the ESM finite element models were also developed by using HYPERMESH, ABAQUS, and 2-D S4 shell elements. The *SHELL

GENERAL SECTION option in ABAQUS was used to define the section behavior and this option takes into account the equivalent stiffness values as input. To avoid complicated full finite element models an approximate analytical method is proposed based on previous static analyses of grid structures by Chen and Tsai [2]. The equivalent stiffness approach gives us a way to calculate the natural frequencies fairly easily and economically. Either we can use these stiffness properties of the grids for a simple 2-D finite element plate model for any boundary conditions or we can use it in closed form frequency equations such as those for symmetric laminated plates with simply supported boundary conditions [3].

Details of the derivation of the equivalent stiffnesses are given in the thesis by Islam [6], and only the key equations are summarized here. The grid structure can be considered as a combination of sets of parallel ribs. The equivalent axial, flexural and torsional stiffnesses of each family of parallel ribs can be calculated separately, and then the overall stiffnesses of the grid structure are obtained by the principle of superposition. Following the analysis by Chen and Tsai [2], consider the family of N parallel ribs in Fig. 3, each of which has center-to-center spacing d , cross-sectional area A , and longitudinal modulus E_x . The direction of the local (x, y, z) coordinate axes are along and perpendicular to the ribs. Let θ be the angle between the local and global axes $(1,2,3)$. It should be noted that the normal strain along the y direction ε_y , the shear strains γ_{xy}, γ_{yz} and the curvature κ_y , were not considered in the ribs. If all N ribs are identical, static equilibrium and geometric compatibility requirements lead to the following equation relating the force per unit length along the x direction to the corresponding strain ε_x [2]

$$N_x = \frac{AE_x \varepsilon_x}{d} \quad (1)$$

In this case, the force per unit length is based on the effective width $(N-1)d + 2e$ for the parallel family of ribs, where the distance e in Fig. 1 approaches $d/2$. Thus, the corresponding effective width becomes approximately Nd . Transforming both the force per unit length and the strain to the global coordinates and factoring out the resulting extensional stiffnesses A_{ij} for an equivalent flat laminated plate,

$$[A] = \frac{E_x A}{d} \begin{bmatrix} m^4 & m^2 n^2 & m^3 n \\ m^2 n^2 & n^4 & mn^3 \\ m^3 n & mn^3 & m^2 n^2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} & A_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where $m = \cos \theta$ and $n = \sin \theta$. Applying a similar approach for bending of the parallel family of ribs, the flexural stiffness matrix for an equivalent flat laminated plate is found to be

$$D = \frac{1}{d} \begin{bmatrix} E_x I m^4 + G J m^2 n^2 & E_x I m^2 n^2 + G J m^2 n^2 & E_x I m^3 n - \frac{G J m n (m^2 - n^2)}{2} \\ E_x I m^2 n^2 - G J m^2 n^2 & E_x I n^4 + G J m^2 n^2 & E_x I m^3 n + \frac{G J m n (m^2 - n^2)}{2} \\ E_x I m^3 n - G J m^3 n & E_x I m^3 n + G J m^3 n & E_x I m^2 n^2 + \frac{G J m^2 (m^2 - n^2)}{2} \\ E_x I m^3 n + G J m n^3 & E_x I m^3 n - G J m n^3 & E_x I m^2 n^2 - \frac{G J n^2 (m^2 - n^2)}{2} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ D_{21} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where

$$J = \frac{hw^3}{16} \left[\frac{16}{3} - 3.36 \frac{w}{h} \left(1 - \frac{w^4}{12h^4} \right) \right] \quad (4)$$

and E_x and G are longitudinal and shear modulus of the rib, respectively; h is rib height, I and J are the moment of inertia with respect to the midplane and the torsional constant of the rib cross section, respectively.

For the orthotropic case, the $[D]$ matrix becomes a 3x3 symmetric matrix with D_{16} , and D_{26} equal to zero. The A_{66} term for the orthogrid must be taken into account because the bending and shear effects of ribs tangential to the midplane cannot be neglected and it becomes as [2].

$$A_{66} = 1/a_{66} \quad (5)$$

where

$$a_{66} = \frac{1}{12} \frac{d_{90}^2 d_0}{E_x I_0'} + \frac{1}{12} \frac{d_{90} d_0^2}{E_x I_0'} + \frac{d_0}{\kappa G A_0} + \frac{d_{90}}{\kappa G A_{90}} \quad (6)$$

G is the shear modulus of the ribs, d_0 and d_{90} are horizontal and vertical spacing of ribs, and κ is the shear correction factor which is taken as 5/6 [2].

The total stiffnesses for the grid can be obtained from superposition by summing up the stiffnesses of each parallel family of ribs taking into account the orientation of each family of ribs. For example the $[A]$ and $[D]$ matrices for the orthogrid with two families of identical ribs at $\theta = 0^\circ$ and 90° are

$$[A]_{orthogrid} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_x A}{d} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{E_x A}{d} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & A_{66} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

$$[D]_{orthogrid} = \frac{1}{d} \begin{bmatrix} E_x I & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & E_x I & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{GJ}{2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Similarly, for the isogrid with three parallel families of identical ribs at $\theta = 0^\circ, 60^\circ$ and -60° ,

$$[A]_{isogrid} = \frac{\sqrt{3}E_x A}{4d} \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

$$[D]_{isogrid} = \frac{\sqrt{3}E_x I}{4d} \begin{bmatrix} 3+\tau & 1+\tau & 0 \\ 1+\tau & 3+\tau & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1+\tau \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

where

$$\tau = \frac{GJ}{E_x I}, \quad I = \frac{1}{12}wh^3 \quad \text{and} \quad J = \frac{hw^3}{16} \left[\frac{16}{3} - 3.36 \frac{w}{h} \left(1 - \frac{w^4}{12h^4} \right) \right] \quad (11)$$

and h is rib height, d is the length of each side of the equilateral triangles in the isogrid, I and J are the moment of inertia with respect to the midplane and torsional constant of the rib cross section, respectively

A simple rectangular plate model having the overall dimensions of grid structures (264 mm × 304 mm) was created by using S4 elements in HYPERMESH [4] with the option *SHELL GENERAL SECTION in ABAQUS [5] to define the section behavior. In this option the thickness per unit length of the grid structure (for actual grid area) and the equivalent stiffness properties calculated by Equations 12-13 for orthogrids and Equations 14-15 for isogrids and were given as input [6]. Then with the appropriate boundary condition the model was analyzed for frequencies and mode shapes. As an additional check, for the case of the simply supported plate, the equivalent stiffnesses were substituted in an existing closed form solution for frequencies [3]. A unidirectional fiber reinforced lamina such as a rib in the grid structure can be treated as an orthotropic material, and the micromechanics approach was used to predict its engineering constants of the ribs from fiber and matrix properties [6].

EXPERIMENTS

Following the thermoplastic stamping concept outlined by Goldsworthy and Hiel [7] the orthogrid and isogrid specimens were made of unidirectional Twintex[®] E-glass/polypropylene material produced by Vetrotex Company. The Twintex[®] unidirectional roving is a unique co-mingled material consisting of thermoplastic polypropylene fibers and unidirectional E-glass fibers. When the material is heated near the melting temperature of the polypropylene, the molten polypropylene fibers flow and form the matrix in the composite. 264 mm × 304 mm steel molds for orthogrids and isogrids were used with same size of top plate, and the co-mingled material was packed in the machined grooves of the molds. The rib width and thickness are 6.4 mm and 6.3 mm respectively, and the rib fiber volume fraction of 0.45 was found from burn-out tests. The material properties of the Twintex[®] unidirectional glass/PP composites of 0.45 fiber volume fraction were estimated by micromechanics models for use in the analytical models. Further details on these models are given in [6] and [8].

The impulse-frequency apparatus shown in Fig. 5 was used to measure the modal frequencies of the grid structures in the free-free boundary condition. A similar setup was used for the cantilever boundary condition, except one side of the grid structure was clamped between two metal plates. Experiments were not conducted for the simply supported boundary condition due to the difficulty in accurately simulating such a condition.

Fig. 5. Impulse-frequency response apparatus for free-free suspension

For the free-free boundary condition, the grids were suspended by thin nylon filaments at small angle (less than 15 degrees) from horizontal plane, otherwise the stiffness of the filaments will come into effect. The miniature accelerometer that was connected to the spectrum analyzer was attached to the grids by using beeswax. Grid specimens were excited with a light impulse, then the modal frequencies were determined from the peaks in frequency response curves on the spectrum analyzer. The position of the accelerometer and the location of impulse were selected carefully to pick up all of the modes (axial, flexural and twisting). References [6] and [8] describe the details of the apparatus and test procedure.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, typical results from the “exact” finite element models and the equivalent stiffness models will be compared with experimental results for both orthogrid and isogrid structures in free-free and cantilever boundary conditions. Some exact and ESM results are also shown for the simply supported boundary condition, and detailed results for all the cases are given in [6]. Convergence studies are important, as finite element analysis is an approximate numerical method. For both isogrid and orthogrid “exact” finite element models, convergence studies were conducted for the free edge boundary condition. These studies were made by refinement of the meshes until the frequencies converge. The free edge condition was chosen for the convergence studies because modal frequencies are very sensitive to slight variations in boundary conditions such as clamped or hinged. To save computation time, models having smaller number of elements were used for other boundary conditions. Convergence studies for ESM models were also performed.

Orthogrid Structures: Table 1 summarizes the predicted frequencies from the convergence studies for both “exact” and ESM models of free-free orthogrids and compares those results with the corresponding experimental values. Note that, for the free-free condition, the first six modes are rigid body modes, so the modes involving material deformation begin with Mode 7.

Table 1. Comparison of predicted and measured frequencies for free-free orthogrids

Type of deformation	Mode	Natural frequencies of orthogrid (Hz)						Experimental
		Model 1 (convergence study)			Model 2 (convergence study)			
		360 elements	2544 elements	10176 elements	500 elements	1020 elements	4080 elements	
Twisting	7*	53.9	53.7	53.5	58.2	58.2	58.2 (8.78%)**	66 (23.36%)
Bending	8	235	231	229	201	201	201 (-12.22%)	240 (4.8%)
Twisting	9	239	235	233	233	233	233 (0%)	250 (7.296%)
Bending	10	280	278	277	268	268	268 (-3.25%)	264 (-4.69%)

Note: Model 1 is the “exact” FE model, and Model 2 is the ESM FE model based on the equivalent stiffnesses given in Equations (7) and (8). The percentage shown in parentheses is the percent difference between either the ESM Model 2 or the experimental value and the 10176 element “exact” Model 1.

The ESM model converges much more rapidly than the exact model, and no changes in predicted frequencies were observed as the number of elements was increased from 500 to 4080. Although not shown here, the free-free mode shapes from the ESM model are in good agreement with those from the exact model. Typical mode shape and frequency results from “exact” and ESM models are shown in Figs. 6-9 for simply supported orthogrids. It is seen that there is reasonably good agreement between the two models for both mode shapes and frequencies.

Fig. 6 Exact finite element model for simply supported orthogrid, first mode, frequency = 167 Hz

Fig. 7 ESM finite element plate model for simply supported orthogrid, first mode, frequency = 156 Hz.

Fig. 8 Exact finite element model for simply supported orthogrid, second mode, frequency = 375 Hz.

Fig. 9 ESM finite element plate model for simply supported orthogrid, second mode, frequency = 388 Hz.

Isogrid Structures: Table 2 summarizes the predicted frequencies from the convergence studies for both “exact” and ESM models of free-free isogrids and compares those results with the corresponding experimental values. Note that, for the free-free condition, the first six modes are rigid body modes, so the modes involving material deformation begin with Mode 7.

Table 2. Comparison of predicted and measured frequencies for free-free isogrids

Type of deformation	Mode	Natural frequencies of isogrid (Hz)						Experimental
		Model 1 (convergence study)			Model 2 (convergence study)			
		1324 elements	5292 elements	10584 elements	500 elements	1020 elements	4080 elements	
Twisting	7*	117	113	115	140	139	139 (20.86%)	140 (21.7%)
Bending	8	170	169	170	183	183	183 (7.65%)	164 (-3.5%)
Twisting	9	248	244	247	271	270	270 (9.34%)	260 (5.26%)
Bending	10	266	258	263	341	341	341 (29.65%)	284 (7.98%)

Note: Model 1 is the “exact” FE model, and Model 2 is the ESM FE model based on the equivalent stiffnesses given in Equations (9) and (10). The percentage shown in parentheses is the percent difference between either the ESM Model 2 or the experimental value and the 10584 element “exact” Model 1.

As with the orthogrid, the ESM model converges much more rapidly than the exact model. However, the differences between the ESM and exact and between experimental and exact are greater than they were for the orthogrid. Typical mode shape and frequency results from “exact” and ESM models are shown in Figs. 10-13 for cantilevered isogrids. It is seen that there is reasonably good agreement between the two models for both mode shapes and frequencies in the first mode, but the predicted second mode frequency by the ESM method is about 17% higher than that predicted by the “exact” model.

Fig. 10 Mode shape (First mode) of free vibration of isogrid under cantilever boundary condition at frequency 39.3 Hz.

Fig. 11 Mode shape (First mode) free vibration of ESM finite element plate model of isogrid under cantilever boundary condition at frequency 41.1 Hz.

Fig. 12 Mode shape (second mode) of free vibration of isogrid under cantilever boundary condition at frequency 78.3 Hz.

Fig. 13 Mode shape (second mode) of free vibration of ESM finite element plate model for isogrid under cantilever boundary condition at frequency 91.3 Hz.

From the above results it can be summarized that the ESM model simulates the “exact” finite element model frequencies reasonably well, but the agreement is better for the orthogrid than for the isogrid. The ESM mode shapes are generally very accurate for the lower modes.

To generate and run the “exact” finite element models takes a considerable amount of time. During the convergence study, it was necessary to increase the element sizes (the largest orthogrid model has 10176 elements and the largest isogrid model has 10584 elements) to converge. The models having large number of elements take hours to run, whereas the ESM model (a simple plate) is very simple to make and convergence occurs very quickly (converged ESM orthogrid model has 500 elements and converged ESM isogrid model has 1020 elements).

It is also observed that the measured frequencies also vary somewhat from the “exact” finite element results and in some cases the ESM gives results that are closer to experimental values. It is important to note that all of the analytical models use input properties which are estimated from micromechanics, and the accuracy of these estimates is not precisely known. The properties may be different from those of the specimens tested. Other factors include the locally higher fiber volume fractions due to rib overlap and extra material at the nodes of the grids. In addition, none of the models included through-the-thickness shear effects, since they were all 2-D models. Related research on integral passive damping in composite grid structures required the use of 3-D finite element models because of the importance of through-the-thickness shear effects on the damping [8]. These effects are also more important for higher modes. In conclusion, it appears that we can apply the ESM models to estimate modal frequencies and mode shapes for orthogrids with reasonable accuracy and for isogrids with somewhat less accuracy.

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